

Graphene Based Electronic Device

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Abstract : The semiconductor industry is placing an increased emphasis on emerging materials and devices that may provide improved performance, or provide novel functionality for devices. Recently, graphene, as a true two-dimensional carbon material, has shown fascinating applications in electronics. In this paper detailed discussions are introduced for possible applications of grapheme Transistor in RF and digital devices.

Keywords : graphene, GFET, RF, digital

Conference Title : ICECE 2014 : International Conference on Electrical and Communication Engineering

Conference Location : Amsterdam, The Netherlands

Conference Dates : August 07-08, 2014